

ELIXIR 2023 Recommended Interoperability Resources

Authors: Clare Garrard¹, Peter Maccallum², Fabio Liberante³

Affiliation: ELIXIR, Wellcome Genome Campus, Hinxton, Cambridge, CB10 1SD, UK

ORCID: ¹ 0000-0001-6561-073X, ² 0000-0001-5260-5915, ³ 0000-0002-0192-5385

Background

In order to achieve FAIRer data, the informatics life science community needs a portfolio of different resources to facilitate linking, integration, and reuse of data, such as the [ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resources](#) (RIRs). The ELIXIR RIR process was first introduced in 2018 in order to identify key life science resources that enable interoperability and has expanded to encompass [FAIR](#)-enabling resources, while still retaining an emphasis on interoperability.

The [ELIXIR RIR Selection Criteria](#) includes 4 key criteria that are used by resource reviewers and evaluators to assess whether a resource can be deemed to be an ELIXIR RIR:

1. Resource Facilitation to Scientific Research
2. Community served
3. Quality of resource
4. Legal framework, funding, and governance

2023 ELIXIR RIRs

The 2023 ELIXIR RIR Process ran for the third time in 2023, and 7 new resources were awarded RIR status, bringing the total number of RIRs to 21. The new ELIXIR RIRs following the 2023 process are listed below, and the full list can be found on the [ELIXIR website](#):

- **Bgee Knowledge Graph:** The Bgee Knowledge Graph provides access to gene expression patterns in multiple animal species and tissue types via a SPARQL endpoint that understands a number of controlled vocabularies and identifiers.

The underlying database results from the integration and harmonisation of several data sources.

- **Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW):** The Data Stewardship Wizard is a tool designed to assist researchers and data stewards in creating smart Data Management Plans (DMPs) for FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) Science. It uses a unique and modular question-based approach to help users to create, plan, and collaborate on DMPs.
- **FAIR Cookbook:** The FAIR Cookbook is an online, open, and live resource for the life sciences, providing “recipes” to help users make and keep data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). Each recipe covers a particular set of steps towards FAIRer data and are indexed according to a particular dataset “maturity” level.
- **European Galaxy Server:** Galaxy is an interoperable open-source platform for scientific data analysis and sharing, covering diverse research fields such as omics, machine learning, and climate science.
- **Jalview:** Jalview is a free, cross-platform (inc. web app) system that connects across different resources, providing visualisation and analysis of biological data. It allows users to conduct integrated analyses of their own data in combination with a variety of public data resources through interoperation, including ENA, Ensembl, PDBe, UniProt, InterPro, and AlphaFoldDB. It supports reproducible science by supporting project files that capture the state of a Jalview session.
- **OpenEBench:** OpenEBench is a multifaceted platform for evaluating life sciences tools from two critical perspectives: scientific performance through community-based benchmarking and software quality through the Software Quality Observatory. It helps ensure the reliability, reproducibility, and effectiveness of tools used for analysis and processing of life science data.
- **RDMkit:** The RDMkit is an open-source, online toolkit for researchers and data stewards, providing Research Data Management (RDM) best practices in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. It encompasses the entire research data lifecycle, from planning and collecting data to storing, preserving, and sharing.

Reviewers & Evaluators for the ELIXIR 2023 RIR Process

As part of the Selection Process for ELIXIR RIRs (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1036595) resources are first reviewed by expert reviewers, and then assessed by an independent panel of international evaluators. The feedback provided by these experts is passed on to resource owners, and has proven valuable in improving the quality of applicant resources, whether awarded RIR status or not.

We would like to publicly acknowledge the vital role played by these experts in the RIR Process.

Reviewers

Pinar Alper (LU)
Munazah Andrabi (UK)
Karel Berka (CZ)
Korbinian Bosl (NO)
Jeff Christiansen (AU)
Paulo Czarnewski (SE)
Maria Doyle (IE)
Jean-François Dufayard (FR)
Elena Ghanaim (US)
Carole Goble (UK)
Niclas Jareborg (SE)
Mijke Jetten (NL)
Elin Kronander (SE)
Paulette Lieby (FR)
Frederique Lisacek (CH)
Allyson Lister (UK)
Ivan Micetic (IT)
Fotis Psomopoulos (GR)
Marek Suchanek (CZ)
Danielle Welter (LU)

Evaluators

Izabela Makalowska (PL)
Bogdan Mirauta (RO)
Kathy Reinold (US)
Juha Törnroos (FI)

Interoperability Platform ExCo

Tony Burdett (EMBL-EBI)
Chris Evelo (NL)
Susanna-Assunta Sansone (UK)